

Online Oral Presentation #3 was presented at the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress, held in Ordu, Türkiye, on May 22–24, 2025, and is part of the proceedings titled: *Proceedings of the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress*.

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Adult immunization is one of the most important public health practices to ensure the sustainability of community health. The 18-25 age range is a period when immunity acquired during childhood begins to decline. The decrease in immunity among university students can also affect community immunity (Shon et al., 2021; Srivastava et al., 2024). Therefore, this study aimed to evaluate university students' knowledge and attitudes regarding adult immunization.

Materials and Methods: This descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted with students at Yozgat Bozok University and currently ongoing. A survey prepared by the researchers based on literature data was administered to students who voluntarily agreed to participate in the study. The survey measured students' knowledge and attitudes towards adult immunization. Numerical data were analyzed using descriptive statistical methods such as standard deviation, mean, and categorical variables expressed as numbers and percentages. The chi-square method was used to evaluate categorical variables, while the student's t-test and one-way ANOVA were applied for numerical variables.

Results: A total of 217 university students participated in the study. Of these, 37.3% (n=81) were between the ages of 18-20, 52.5% (n=114) were between 21-23 years old, and 10.1% (n=22) were 24 years or older. Regarding their faculties, 8.8% (n=19) were from the Faculty of Economics and Administrative Sciences, 15.7% (n=34) from the Faculty of Communication, 10.1% (n=22) from the Faculty of Theology, 33.2% (n=72) from the Faculty of Engineering and Architecture, 13.8% (n=30) from the Faculty of Agriculture, and 18.4% (n=40) from the Faculty of Education. Of the students 88.9% (n=193) reported that they had not received any education about adult immunization during their university education. About 49.8% (n=108) of the students knew that adult vaccines could be administered at family health centers, while 42.4% (n=92) were undecided about getting vaccines that they would have to pay for themselves. Students who believed that vaccines should only be given to the elderly in emergency situations had lower average attitude scores, which was statistically significant. Similarly, students who thought that no vaccines should be administered during pregnancy had lower average attitude scores, which was also statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: University students lack sufficient knowledge about immunization. Providing information about adult immunization during university education and in healthcare settings will contribute to raising awareness among university students about acquiring individual immunity. It will also help increase the number of immunized individuals in society, thereby supporting the sustainability of community immunity.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Adult immunisation, university student, preventive medicine

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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